

On the Fourfit fringe search in HOPS

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1 Introduction

The HOPS post-processing system includes a program called `fourfit` to do fringe fitting. This document is an attempt to translate what `fourfit` does into terms comprehensible to those of us raised in the AIPS/CASA tradition.

This work was prompted by a recent memo from Bill Petrachenko (Petrachenko, 2023), but HOPS continues to be actively developed in the context of the VGOS and EHT arrays (Cappallo, 2014, Blackburn et al., 2019), so it still makes sense to try to understand their tools.

Cappallo's `fourfit` manual (Cappallo, 2017) states:

In the late 70's Alan Rogers developed a program called FRNGE derived from the original VLBI2 fringe-fitting program. [...] As both hardware and software technology improved it became apparent that FRNGE would need to be rewritten, and so `fourfit` was created by Colin Lonsdale, Roger Cappallo, and Cris Niell in the early 90's. The basic algorithms were adopted directly from FRNGE, while the I/O, control architecture and plotting were heavily modified. The programming language was changed from FORTRAN to C.

This much, at least, is reassuringly familiar: the present author was personally responsible for borrowing the algorithms and to some extent the FORTRAN code of AIPS FRING (no direct relation to FRNGE as far as I know) routine to develop the CASA `fringefit` task.

And while there doesn't seem to be any paper that admits to being an account of the VLBI2 software or of FRNGE (and Cappallo's manual doesn't cite any papers at all), there *is* Rogers' 1970 paper, which gives an account of fringe-fitting and was presumably the foundation of the VLBI2 software by the same author.

VLBI was a newer technology in 1970 than it is now (by about fifty years) and Rogers' account of fringe-fitting ranges over correlation itself, the optimal spacing of what we now call IFs (in AIPS) or spectral windows (in CASA), bandpass correction and more. The account given here, though, is only concerned with how the fringe-fitting algorithm is organised.

2 2D FFT explained idiosyncratically

We start with correlation products for antennas x and y as a function of frequency, ω for every integration time (or “accumulation period”) t_3 for each spectral window, k (a “frequency channel”) for Rogers. The integration times for the visibilities range over some range T_4 for a given fringe-fit, corresponding to a “solution interval” in CASA.

Suppose we have a (somewhat unknown) residual delay rate R and a residual delay τ (in addition to the *a priori* geometrical delay used for correlation).

We begin by taking the Fourier transform of $S_{xy}(\omega, t_3)$ with respect to time to get a function $S'_k(\omega, R)$ w.r.t. R , where we are already adjusting Rogers’ notation slightly to match our AIPS-centric way of thinking.

In Rogers’ notation, $S'^{t_4}_k(\omega, R)$ is written as $S_{k,R}(\omega)$; since he does not want to have a two-dimensional functional form for S , R becomes instead a parameter.

$$S'_k(\omega, R) = \left(\frac{1}{T_4} \right) \sum_{t_3}^{T_4} S_{xy}(\omega, t_3) \exp(-i\omega_k^0 R t_3) \quad (1)$$

Then we take the Fourier transform of $S'_k(\omega, R)$ in the ω -dimension to transform it to $S''_k(\tau, R)$.

$$S''_k(\tau, R) = \sum_{\omega}^W S'_k(\omega, R) B(\omega) e^{-i\omega\tau} \exp(-i\omega_k^0 \tau) \quad (2)$$

Note that the bandpass function $B(\omega)$ has been folded into this FFT. The bandpass correction can be done at various stages of calibration; this is very much one of them.

Rogers defines a delay function, $D_R(\tau)$ as the sum of S'' over the various subbands k :

$$D_R(\tau) = \frac{1}{KW} \sum_k^K S''(\tau, R) \quad (3)$$

Then we define

$$D(\tau) = \max |D_R(\tau)| \quad (4)$$

So for each delay we have maximized over the delay-rate (R) dimension. Then we look for the maximum of $D(\tau)$ over τ to find the best-fit delay, and set the delay-rate to be the one chosen for that τ in Equation 4.

You might say: “Isn’t this a complicated way to describe finding a peak of the 2D FFT of the visibilities in time and frequency?”. And I would say “Yes, that’s basically what it is. They just didn’t *have* two dimensions back in 1970 so they couldn’t just say so.”

3 Some wrinkles

But that’s not quite true. It would be true for a single subband, but in fact in Equation 4 we stack all the bands, suitably phase-rotated, to get a multiband delay. (I don’t think this is as good as concatenating the subbands, to be honest.)

Also, the fact that the HOPS algorithm is conceptualized as a search over a grid of accumulation periods t_3 and frequencies ω with FFTs done on demand leads to a very different looking implementation and has allowed the latest version of HOPS to fold in an additional search dimension over dispersive delay.

The HOPSers also implement a grid-refinement strategy to improve their fit for delay and delay-rate. I don't understand this well enough to describe it, but it serves in practice as a (per-baseline) alternative to the HOPS/CASA least-squares stage.

References

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